

Stent Patency In Endoscopic Sphincterotomy Versus No Endoscopic Sphincterotomy In Malignant Biliary Obstruction

Erum Kazim, Aftab Ahmed Leghari, Imrana Zulfikar, Raheel Ahmed, Ayesha Majeed, Shahriyar Ghazanfar

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 05, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Endoscopic Sphincterotomy, ERCP, Stent, Patency</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6519258</p>	<p>Objective: To evaluate stent patency with and without endoscopic sphincterotomy in malignant biliary obstruction.</p> <p>Methods: This prospective study was conducted in Endoscopy Suite, Surgical Unit IV, Civil Hospital Karachi from April, 2021 to January, 2022 for a period of 10 months. Patients undergoing ERCP for inoperable malignant biliary obstruction were randomized into EST group and non EST group. Stent patency was the primary end point. Patients were evaluated for resolution of jaundice, bleeding, perforation, pancreatitis and cholangitis. Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS version 22.</p> <p>Results: Total number of patients was 83. Out of which 48 patients were in EST group and 35 in non EST group. 55 pts were male and 28 were female with a mean age of 64.2 ± 7.2 yrs. Stent patency was higher in non EST group (74.28% vs 68% $P < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in other complications between the two groups.</p> <p>Conclusion: In our study stent patency was significantly higher in non EST group.</p>

Introduction

Malignant biliary obstruction is a common cause of obstructive jaundice. Pancreatic carcinoma, Periampullary carcinoma, Cholangiocarcinoma, Gallbladder carcinoma and metastatic disease are the common etiologies of malignant biliary obstruction¹. The presentation varies from painless jaundice to pruritis, cholangitis and other debilitating symptoms. Mostly patients present in advanced stage and only less than 20% patients are candidate for surgery². The prognosis is very poor as the patients with unresectable disease survive only 6 months³. Whereas sometimes the patients with resectable disease are unfit for surgery because of medical comorbidities they require some time to optimize before surgery. Whether the disease is resectable or advanced, delay in treatment results in increase in morbidity and mortality. In either settings biliary decompression is needed⁴. Biliary stenting via Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) has now become the preferred treatment for biliary decompression⁵. Endoscopic biliary stenting is less invasive, cost beneficial procedure compared to surgical palliative procedures⁶. Biliary stenting improves the quality of life by decreasing cholestasis, pruritis and other symptoms of obstruction⁷.

Mostly 10 Fr stent is placed in distal bile duct obstruction. Many endoscopists routinely perform endoscopic sphincterotomy before stent placement after gaining access to bile duct⁸. ERCP whether done with or without sphincterotomy carries several complications as post procedure pancreatitis, bleeding, perforation⁹. Studies show that ES reduces the risk of post ERCP pancreatitis¹⁰ whereas other studies show that routine ES increases the risk of complications in patients presenting with malignant biliary obstruction¹¹.

There is controversy regarding doing sphincterotomy before stenting. A breached sphincter in patients with EST may lead to bacterial invasion from the duodenum, and an increased risk of acute cholangitis at the early stage of stent placement^{11,12}. With the expansion of stent and tumor growth, this phenomenon may decrease gradually. Other possible reasons for stent occlusion may include the formation of biliary sludge, tumor ingrowth or overgrowth, and epithelial hyperplasia inside the stent^{13,14}.

The current study was planned to evaluate the stent patency rate and complications on patients with malignant biliary obstruction undergoing procedure with and without endoscopic sphincterotomy.

Methods and Materials:

This observational comparative study was conducted in Endoscopy Suite, Surgical Unit IV, Civil Hospital Karachi from April 2021 to January, 2022 for a period of 1 year after the approval from Institutional Review Board of Dow University of Health Sciences. The study was done on the patients who underwent ERCP and stenting for malignant biliary obstruction. Pregnant females, Children below the age of 18 yrs and patients in

whom stenting could not be done were excluded from the study. We had a Sample size of 80 with confidence interval of 95% and margin error of 5% on raosoft sample calculator.

All patients who present with malignant biliary obstruction were randomly allocated with an envelope method to either Group A (EST)or Group B (non EST). An independent observer recorded the data. Post procedure amylase was done at 12hours. Stent patency was the primary end point and was checked by follow up visits monthly for 3 months. Symptoms of yellow discoloration, dark urine and fever with chills and raised LFTS were considered as blocked stent. Pancreatitis, bleeding, perforation and cholangitis were secondary end points. Clinical records were evaluated for demographic data, complications and success related to this procedure.

All ERCP procedures were done by standard technique which included written and informed consent from all the patients. Procedure was performed under deep sedation with propofol given by the anesthetist specialist. Antibiotic prophylaxis was with intravenous Ceftriaxone. ERCP was performed by TJF. Q- 180-V duodenoscope (Olympus). The contrast medium Urografin was used for the opacification of hepatobiliary system. Scope was placed in the duodenum and selective biliary cannulation was achieved with guide wire technique. Position of stricture was assessed by doing cholangiogram. In Group A patients cannula was exchanged with sphincterotome (Olympus ESG-100). Sphincterotomy was done elctrosurgically. Then plastic biliary stent was placed. While in Group B cannula was not exchanged with sphincterotome.

Our primary outcome was to observe stent patency in patients with or without end sphincterotomy.

Technical Success was defined as complete access and successful placement of plastic stent within the common bile duct. Clinical success was defined as clinical improvement or declining pattern of LFTS which was done after one month and three months. Intra procedure bleeding was defined as bleeding that occurred during the procedure and needed some intervention to control. Post procedure bleeding was defined as the bleeding that was documented after procedure within 1 week and needed admission.

All data has been entered in statistical software SPSS version 22 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Clinical records were evaluated according to age, gender, signs and symptoms, indications and imaging modalities used and complications including bleeding, perforation, infection, pancreatitis. Statistical analysis included mean with standard deviation and median with interquartile ranges for continuous variables. Frequency analysis included percentages for categorical variables. P value of less than 0.05 was regarded as statistically significant.

Results:

In our study total number of patients was 83 out of which 48 (57.8%) patients underwent EST before placing the biliary stent and in 35 (42.1%) patients EST was not done. All of the patients presented with malignant biliary obstruction.

We did ERCP and stenting for malignant biliary obstruction in total 83 patients. Out of which 55 were male and 28 were females with the mean age of 64.2 ± 7.2 years . The frequency of different malignancies with which the patients presented is shown in table I.

Diagnosis

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Vali Cholangiocarcinoma	29	34.9	34.9	34.9
Peri ampullary Tumor	25	30.1	30.1	65.1
pancreatic malignancy	15	18.1	18.1	83.1
Gall bladder Carcinoma	8	9.6	9.6	92.7
blie duct stricture	6	7.2	7.2	100.0
Total	83	100.0	100.0	

48(57.8%) patients underwent endoscopic sphincterotomy while in 35 (42.2%) patients sphincterotomy was not done.

Procedure

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
sphincterotomy	48	57.8	57.8	57.8

No Sphincterotomy	35	42.2	42.2	100.0
Total	83	100.0	100.0	

Stent was patent in 33(68%) patients who underwent sphincterotomy and in 26(74.28%) patients who were in non EST group.

Procedure * Patency Crosstabulation

Count

		Patency		Total
		Stent Patent	stent blocked	
Procedure	sphincterotomy	33	15	48
	No Sphincterotomy	26	9	35
Total		59	24	83

Pancreatitis was developed in 2% (1/48) of our patient who underwent sphincterotomy and in 8.57% (3/35) patients in non EST group. In our study bleeding was 2.08% (1/48) in EST group. None of the patient in non EST group had bleeding. 33.33% (16/48) patient developed cholangitis in EST group and 31.42% (11/35) in non EST group.

Procedure * Complications Crosstabulation

Procedure * Complications Crosstabulation

Count

		Complications				Total
		Bleeding	cholangitis	pancreatitis	no complications	
Procedure	sphincterotomy	1	16	1	30	48
	No Sphincterotomy	1	11	3	20	35
Total		2	27	4	50	83

Bar Chart

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.329 ^a	1	.037		
Continuity Correction ^b	3.398	1	.065		
Likelihood Ratio	4.482	1	.034		
Fisher's Exact Test				.057	.031
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.277	1	.039		
N of Valid Cases	83				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 11.39.

Author Information

Dr. Erum Kazim

Assistant Professor Surgery, Surgical Unit IV

Dr. Aftab Ahmed Leghari

Chief Medical Officer, Surgical Unit IV

Dr. Imrana Zulfikar

Associate Professor, Unit 4

Dr. Raheel Ahmed

Consultant, Unit 4

Dr. Ayesha Majeed

Postgraduate Resident, Surgical IV

Dr. Shahriyar GhazanfarProfessor, Surgical Unit IV
